

Vasco da Gama

by H. Reade

Reade, H. Vasco Da Gama.

The Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, 1898, 589–604.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25208011>

This biography of Vasco da Gama was identified in a project to collect early historical descriptions of scurvy. Symptoms consistent with scurvy were recorded during the first voyage of Vasco da Gama. Charles Nowell (1940) criticized several earlier biographies of Vasco da Gama and commented that the biography by H. Reade was “Somewhat better”.¹ However, the version available through the above link is particularly difficult to read and therefore this easy-to-read version was made.

This text is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779398>

2025-12-1

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

1 <https://doi.org/10.2307/2506808>

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<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Vasco-da-Gama>

<https://exploration.marinersmuseum.org/subject/vasco-da-gama/>

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<https://doi.org/10.2307/2543592>

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ART. XXIV. — *Vasco da Gama.* By H. READE, F.R.G.S.

VASCO DA GAMA, though not a man of words, was, as Camoens² says, a man of strenuous deeds, and it is for the sake of his deeds, and of the results which during four centuries have flowed from them, that we are now commemorating him. We celebrate in him the man whose courage and perseverance gave India to Europe and to England, and who, all unknowingly, was, with Columbus and Magellan, one of the three men who saved the Europe of the Renaissance and of the Reformation from being laid in ruins by Turkish tyranny seconded by French treachery. Had not Columbus and Da Gama, twenty years before the battle of Mohacs³ and the successes of Barbarossa⁴ in the Mediterranean, bestowed upon Spain and Portugal the riches of Asia and America, Charles V could never have hurled back from the German frontiers and the Italian coasts the all but overwhelming inrush of the hordes of Suleiman the Magnificent.⁵ But what could the defenders of Christendom have done save for the coffers of the Fuggers⁶ and the Welsers,⁷ of the bankers of Antwerp and the bankers of Genoa? and whence did these derive their wealth but from the newly-opened Spice Islands of the East and the new-found gold-mines of the West? By discovering the sea road to India, Vasco da Gama made Lisbon and Antwerp the emporia⁸ of the world. In 1517 the Turks conquered Egypt, and thus closed the last of the roads along which the world's wealth had of old passed from East to West. But twenty-five years earlier the loss of this Eastern trade would have paralyzed the strength of Germany and of Italy, at the very moment when the fall of Hungary and the treason of

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Francis I were to leave the walls of Vienna and Doria's galleys as the only bulwarks between Turkish savagery and the printing-presses of Basle, the studios glowing with the canvasses of Titian, and the universities where the germs of our modern civilization were just bursting into vigorous life. But the tender plant of culture did not thus perish. Thanks to Vasco da Gama, who had formed new trade

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2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lu%C3%ADs_de_Cam%C3%B5es

3 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Moh%C3%A1cs

4 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hayreddin_Barbarossa

5 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Suleiman_the_Magnificent

6 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fugger_family

7 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Welser_family

8 Emporium. A large retail store selling a wide variety of goods.

routes far beyond the reach of the Sultan's power, Europe at this most critical moment was not deprived of the riches of the East. "The Kings of the Isles could still send their presents, Arabia and Saba could still bear their gifts" to the foot of the Cross; and thus strengthened, Europe was able to stand up against the utmost efforts of her foes. Vasco da Gama, then, was one of the chief saviours of our modern civilization, nor need I remind you how in later years Holland drew from her Eastern trade the strength which enabled her to break the yoke of Louis XIV from off the neck of Europe, nor bow the wealth of India in the hands of England helped her to free our continent from the tyranny of Napoleon.

Vasco da Gama was not only a saviour of civilization; with Albuquerque⁹ and Almeida¹⁰ he was one of the first pioneers on the road which, in the end, led England to her Empire in the East. He it was who taught Europe how to conquer and how to hold the East. To the detriment of his own country he failed to teach Europe a lesson she has not yet learned, and which, perhaps, will never be learned by any race of Latin or of Teutonic¹¹ blood. He failed to perceive how Europe was to rule Asia sympathetically and with the consent of the Asiatics, and his failure in the end cost Portugal the Empire he had won her in the East.

Yet Vasco da Gama was the first discoverer of the true means of utilizing sea power as the foundation of a colonial empire. He clearly saw that when a commercial nation can send its goods more cheaply by sea than by land, and at the same time fails to maintain an efficient fleet, its independence is practically at the mercy of any power which can, by means of its navy, control the routes along

which those goods are conveyed to their markets. Knowing, as he did full well, the unchanging meteorological and oceanographic conditions of the Indian Ocean, he clearly saw that by stationing a few caravels on the trade routes into which these conditions forced the clumsy vessels of Ormuz, of Jeddah, and of Tor, and by securing for these caravels a fortified port—he only asked for one, Calicut,¹² Cochin,¹³ or Cranganor¹⁴—to which they could withdraw at need, Portugal might secure for herself the control of the whole coastline of the Asiatic and of the African world, and with the control of the coastline that of the vast hinterlands, whose well-being depended upon the unchecked flow of trade through their natural ports. These hinterlands she could rule indirectly through their native kings,

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9 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Afonso_de_Albuquerque

10 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Francisco_de_Almeida

11 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teutons>

12 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kozhikode>

13 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kochi>

14 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kodungallur>

secure in her knowledge that she could at any time enforce the unquestioning obedience of her vassals, by closing the trade routes by which they lived. His theories were carried into practice, and eleven years after his discovery of India the victory of Chaul¹⁵ transferred the sceptre of the world's commerce from Egypt and from Venice to Portugal.

The discovery of the value of those factories, which in his day served all the purposes of our modern coaling stations, is also mainly due to Vasco da Gama.

Look out on the map the former seats of Portuguese power. You will see that they correspond, for the most part, as nearly as the requirements of those days will allow, with the strategic points which are of prime importance in the eyes of our naval scientists to-day. In the sixteenth century, sheltered ports of a moderate depth, which could be reached without the necessity of contending with adverse currents, or with adverse winds, were those best fitted to meet the wants of the Portuguese seamen, and so it comes to pass that the only world centre of any actual importance which was known to but left unoccupied by them was Table Bay; probably they failed to annex it because their heavy carracks were ill-suited for struggling on to India against the Mozambique current, or for beating up against the gales which so often rage

around the Cape of Storms.¹⁶ But to look elsewhere, it is only since the introduction of our modern steamships, that is to say, for all practical purposes, within the last thirty years, that, on the East African Coast, Delagoa Bay, Beira, and Zanzibar have replaced Sofala, Mozambique, Kilwa, Mombassa, and Melinde as important centres. Now, of these five, four were chosen by Vasco da Gama and his predecessor, Pero de Covilham,¹⁷ as suitable sites for Portuguese factories; nor were their selections less happy on the Indian coast. It is true that the naval power of Timoja¹⁸ forced Da Gama to refrain from occupying Goa; but Calicut, and even Cochin, were far more suitable centres than Bombay would have been for the spice trade with the Further East; and, indeed, Bombay could only rise into importance when the enterprise of Waghorn had established steam communication with Suez, and when

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15 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Chaul

16 The Portuguese, through not occupying Table Bay, lost the command of the healthy routes which lend thence into the interior of Africa, and were thus forced to content themselves with ports which are separated from the plateaux of the interior by "Fly Belts" and marshes. This is probably the explanation of their failure as colonists in Africa to which Lord Loch has alluded. Mossamedes, the one really healthy port in Portuguese Africa, was completely off the route taken by ships going to India.

Mossamedes:

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mo%C3%A7%C3%A2medes>

17 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/P%C3%A0ro_da_Covilh%C3%A3

18 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Timoji>

the railway had been carried through the Western Ghats. In our great-grandfathers' day, Madras and Surat, the successor of Cambay, were far more important to our trade than was the "Good Bay" which had passed to England in the dowry of Catherine of Braganza.

Yet even more important results of Vasco da Gama's voyage remains to be mentioned. Portugal was in the fifteenth century the one world power whose genius fitted her to serve us an intermediary between the East and the West.

France, England, and Germany, wasted by centuries of foreign war and of civil broils, and as yet but little civilized in comparison with the nations of Southern Europe, were in no ways fitted to undertake the task of colonizing lands densely peopled with races which in many respects were far more civilized than themselves. The hard, unyielding temper of the Teutonic races had sufficiently shown

its inability to adapt itself to altered conditions and surroundings in Ireland, in Poland, in Bohemia, and in the Baltic provinces. Italy, a nation of statesmen, of bankers, and of merchants, was divided into a crowd of rival states, whose commercial jealousies had already, three centuries before, rendered them unable to profit by the magnificent inheritance which had come to them at the capture of Constantinople, whilst the Papacy, itself an Italian power, and owing its existence solely to the skilful adjustment of the balance of power between its rivals in the Peninsula, would have been utterly unable to carry out the task of partitioning two new worlds between Venice and Genoa, between Florence, Milan, and Naples. It was a Spanish and not an Italian pope who signed the Borgian Grant. Spain, embittered by her secular struggle against the Jew and the Moor, was but an ill training-school for men who would be called upon to govern lands tilled with civilized Pagans, with followers of Mahomet allied by religious sympathy, if not by actual ties of blood, with her own lately conquered vassals of Granada, and with Christians, who bowing the knee as they did to the successors of St. Thomas, but not to the successors of St. Peter, were to rigid Catholics more hateful than even infidel, heathen, or Jew. Had Columbus really reached the eastern shores of Asia, and had it fallen to the lot of Spain to undertake the conquest of the lands of Chathai and of Zeiton, of the Great Khan and the Great Mogul, Spanish "Inquisitors" and Spanish "Conquistadores" would in a few years have rendered the future rule of a European nation over India for ever as impossible as the memory of the Jesuits has rendered it over Japan or over Abyssinia, or as centuries of "passive resistance" may render it in China. Only Portugal remained. For

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three hundred years her soil had been free from the presence of the Moor; her ecclesiastics were far removed from the ambitions and from the influence of the Roman Curia; her kings, since the first conquest of Ceuta,¹⁹ had been guided in their self-imposed task of world exploration

by wise men trained in the schools of the Torah and of the Koran, and had not scorned to seek the advice of pagans as to the means of reaching the Christian realms ruled over by Prester John.²⁰ Vasco da Gama's own expedition had, indeed, been chiefly decided on in consequence of information obtained by John II from the pagan king of Benin during his visit to Portugal in 1484, and his instructions had been drawn up by Don Manoel in consultation with the learned Hebrew astronomer Abraham-ben-Zaccuth. The fire of the Catholic faith burned brightly in Portugal, but in the fifteenth century the Portuguese were, as yet, far from being a fanatical race, and though Vasco da Gama might be eager to bear the Standard of the Cross through the length and breadth of Asia and Africa, yet we never find him, except, perhaps, in one or two instances for political reasons, forcing unwilling converts to the baptismal font. His men, many of whom had already lived in friendly intercourse with the negroes of Manicongo,²¹ interested themselves whilst in Calicut in obtaining vocabularies of the native language and in drawing up memoirs on the geography and commerce of the Further East from information obtained from friendly Moors. Thus the way was paved for a system of alliances between the Portuguese and the native kings, which materially facilitated the introduction of European rule and European religion into India, and which certainly could not have been established by any other Europeans of that day. The unknown author of the "Roteiro," compiling with the help of his Moorish and Jewish friends his scanty notes on Eastern Geography and his scantier vocabulary of Malayalim, was the true forerunner of St. Francis Xavier, of Gonçalvo da Silveira, of Sir William Jones, of Professor Max Müller, and of Sir William Hunter. The Archbishop who burnt the Aztec Manuscripts, the Governor who cast the art treasures of Cuzco into the melting-pot, were Spaniards; but the discoverer of Sanskrit, the first philosopher who conjectured, in some measure, the tie of blood which unites the Aryan peoples of India

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and the West, was an Italian Jesuit, working under the protection of the Portuguese Viceroy of Goa. It was, indeed, fortunate alike for Europe and for the East that

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19 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ceuta>

20 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prester_John

21 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manikongo>

it was Portugal who was called upon by Providence to take upon herself the task of pulling down the barrier which had so long kept apart the two worlds.²²

But what manner of man was Vasco da Gama in himself?

For my part I believe that we find him as he lived and breathed, rather in the simple words of the “Roteiro,” than in Correa’s exaggerations, in the rhetoric of Da Barros, or even in the glowing poetry of the “Lusiad,” albeit that, with true poetic insight, Camoens appears to have kept closely in many places to the sober words of the oldest journal of the voyage. If we could be sure that this journal is really the one compiled by Dom John Figueira, who seems to have been one of the chaplains to the expedition, which Correa professes to have used as the foundation on which he reared his “Indian Memoirs,” we could accept it as a true portrait of Vasco da Gama with very little hesitation, but, unfortunately, the authorship of the “Roteiro” will, in all probability, never be satisfactorily ascertained.

Taking, then, Vasco da Gama as we find him in the “Roteiro,” I seem to see a plain seaman, to whom the task of leading the expedition, which was destined to open the sea road to India, appears to have fallen very much by chance. Correa, indeed, states that he was entrusted with the command merely because he happened to enter the room where King Manoel²³ was deliberating with his council on the coming expedition, and, as Mr. Stanley²⁴ points out, this view is shared by Camoens, who makes Da Gama say:—

“I, whose foreboding heart would still project
Great things like this, as if for me designed,
But who had scarcely hoped to give effect
To such ambitious longings of my mind.

I know not for what reason, what respect,
Or what good omen in my star divined,
The King entrusted to my hands the key
Of this reluctant stubborn mystery.”

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Lusiad, canto iv, 77. (Quillinan.)²⁵

Others say that he simply took the place of his father, Estevam da Gama, who had been named to the command,

22 “Lusiad,” anto vii, 3.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Os_Lus%C3%ADadas

23 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manuel_I_of_Portugal

24 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_Stanley,_3rd_Baron_Stanley_of_Alderley

25 <https://archive.org/details/lusiadluisdecam00adamgoog/page/n174/mode/2up>

but who died before the expedition was ready to sail. However this may be, Da Gama had evidently not made any special studies to fit himself for his task. Unlike Columbus, he had not pored for years over the pages of Strabo, of Ptolemy, of Seneca, and of Cardinal d'Ailly; he was not the correspondent of Toscanelli, nor would he have been prepared to defend the existence of a sea road to India before an assembly of theologians by combating the "dictamina" of Lactantius and of Saint Augustine with quotations drawn from Holy Writ. On the contrary, he know nothing of the literature existing on the subject of India even in his own day, had certainly never read either Josafat Barbara or Niccolo Conti, and possibly had never even heard of Marco Polo, but had prepared himself for his tasks solely by consulting the reports, invaluable it is true, of his predecessors, Bartholomew Diaz,²⁶ Joam Ynfante, and Pero de Covilham, or, at most, by studying Martin Behaim's globe and some faulty copy of Fra Mauro's map.²⁷ If we may judge from an incidental description of the geography of the Indian Ocean in the "Roteiro" (cf. p. 49, ed. 1861), it is very doubtful if he even knew of the existence of the Persian Gulf, unless, indeed, he confounded it with that of Cambay, and he evidently was ignorant of the name of the Koran, or he would have used it in speaking of the "books of their law," which he captured in the Moorish pirogues at Mozambique (cf. "Roteiro," p. 33, ed. 1861).

He shows not the slightest trace of any literary knowledge. All his comparisons and similes are derived from his practical experience in Portugal. The birds and

dogs at St. Helena Bay (cf. "Roteiro," p. 5, ed. 1861 are "pretty well the same as those of Portugal." At Mossel Bay he buys a black bullock, "the beef of which was as tasty as our own in Portugal" (cf. p. 11). The riding oxen of the Hottentot ladies "are as large as those of Alemtejó, and have pack-saddles like those used in Castille" (cf. p. 13); and the shore of Cape Delgado is fringed with trees "like elms" (cf. p. 30). He is entirely ignorant of the existence of any religions save those of Mahomet and of Christ. All that is not Moorish must, therefore, necessarily be Christian: and under the name of Christian he confounds together, with charming, if ignorant, impartiality, the Kali-worshipping Hindoos of Calicut (cf. p. 56, etc.); the devotees of Krishna, whom he voluntarily hails as "Christ" when he meets them at Melinde (cf. p. 47); the Buddhists of the Indo-Chinese Peninsula in Pegu (cf. p. 111) and Siam

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26 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bartolomeu_Dias

27 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fra_Mauro
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fra_Mauro_map

("Xarnauz," p. 109); the Abyssinian Jacobites of the East African coast (at Mombassa, p. 41); and the Christians of St. Thomas, in Southern India ("Quorongoliz," "Coleu," "Cael," p. 108). On his first arrival at Calicut, he attends a ceremony in honour of Kali at the Tali Pagoda, in the full belief that he is assisting at the Christian Mass: he allows his head to be smeared with the sacred sandal-wood paste; describes the "thread of the thrice-born" worn by the Quafees as "a stole, such as is worn by our deacons"; and adores in an image of Gunpâti the Blessed Virgin and her Blessed Son. He merely remarks incidentally that the pictures of the saints drawn in fresco "on the walls of the church were in a different style to ours, for although they wore halos, yet their teeth were so long that they stuck an inch out of their mouths, and every saint had four or five arms" (cf. pp. 56, 57). The spiritual director of the Zamorim is described "as a squat old man who is like a bishop, and by whom the king is directed in all church matters" (cf. p. 58), just as if he had been the Indian equivalent of Dom Manoel's own confessor, Bishop Culçadilha himself. We can well imagine how Vasco da

Gama would have laughed at the fine speeches and classical comparisons, in the best style of Sunnazzaro or of Jorge de Montemayor, which Camoens so often puts in his mouth.

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On the other hand, although he might be neither a philosopher nor a savant, Vasco da Gama had a keen eye for economic facts. The description of the route followed by the spice trade up the Red Sea (cf. p. 88), and the notes on the trade of the Bay of Bengal and Indo-Chinese Peninsula (cf. pp. 107-113), are admirable; and his observations on the essential poverty of India, drawn from the conduct of the beggars of Calicut (cf. p. 77, etc.) in begging scraps from his sailors, would have appeared strange to the contemporaries of Edmund Burke. He takes a great interest in the habits and customs of the nations he visits, as we see from his remarks on the Hottentots and Caffres, on the Moors of the East African coast, and the Indians of Calicut; and knows well that the great advantage which Portugal will derive from his discovery is, that it will transfer the spice trade of the Further East from Venice and Alexandria to Lisbon, although it is evident that he thinks India itself far poorer than the East African coast, at least so far as its own natural productions are concerned. For the rest, he appears to have been well acquainted with the Mediterranean and its peoples; knows the difference between the Arabic spoken in Spain and that current in the Hedjaz; and is aware that the language of Manicongo is identical with that of the Caffres on the Limpopo. His astrolabe he can use well, and he takes some interest in the history

of birds. Thanks to Fra Mauro's map, he has the geography of Africa at his fingers' ends. In short, Vasco da Gama is the type of the navigator who has received the education given at such schools as that which we know Columbus had kept at Lisbon in his youth, but who had never gone through the classical curriculum reserved in his day for those who desired to enter either Holy Orders or the Civil Service of the Crown. We may safely say that but for the previous explorations of Pero de Covilham

and Joam Ynfante, Vasco da Gama would never, by his own unaided exertions, have found out the sea road to India. He could not of himself have devised a plan for doing so; but he was the very man to carry through such a plan when it had been drawn up for him by others.

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If I may be allowed to compare him with a man known in our modern world I should say that Vasco da Gama must greatly have resembled Mr. Cecil Rhodes. Like Mr. Rhodes, Vasco da Gama was a man of indomitable perseverance,²⁸ and was, in the domain of statesmanship, a man of singularly original ideas, who relied solely and entirely on his own efforts. In his Indian diplomacy he had to invent everything, as he had no precedents whatsoever to guide him, save such as he might draw from the intercourse of the Portuguese with the half-savage potentates of Benin and Manicongo; yet, like Mr. Rhodes, he was able to devise the means by which a great empire was built up on an undertaking which, in its origin, had been purely commercial. Out of the arrangements necessary for reorganizing the spice trade in the interests of Portugal, Vasco da Gama shaped the foundations of her Empire in the East, as Mr. Rhodes reared Rhodesia upon the consolidation of the diamond mining companies of Kimberley. Like the South African statesman, he was, perhaps, not over scrupulous when he thought the interests of his country at stake. His conduct at Calicut recalls many episodes in recent history in South Africa.

Lenient as he was, as a rule, to those under him, he could at times be terribly severe. His courage during the mutiny off the Cape, and during his detention on shore at Calicut by the king's intendant, deserves all praise. With the native races he seems to have been not unpopular, although he could, when necessity demanded, display a rigour which might seem cruelty to men who have not lived through such experiences as the Matabili rising and the Indian Mutiny. He was far from being intolerant,

and won the friendship of Moors like Monçaide and the King of Melinde, and of Jews like Don Gaspar das Indias, and seems to have been greatly liked by the Hindoo

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28 "Lusiad," canto vi, 95-99.

fishermen of the Goa coast; but to treachery or suspected treachery he was implacable, as he showed only too plainly at Mossel Bay, at Mozambique, and in his attack on Timoja's fleet (cf. "Roteiro," pp. 12-30, etc.; 93). In bombarding Magadoxo (cf. p. 102), he appears to have been guilty of a wanton piece of cruelty. One is glad to feel that, in many instances, Da Barros does not confirm the accounts given by Correa of Da Gama's treatment of his prisoners, and that we may, for instance, reasonably doubt Correa's assertions (cf. "Lendas da India," Second Voyage, pp. 329-331, Hon. H. Stanley's translation) as to the tortures inflicted by him on the Brahmin envoy of the King of Calicut, and as to the murder of his Malabari prisoners. He was, however, fully authorized by the habits and customs of his own day in inflicting torture on suspected spies, as in the case of his hostages at Mombassa (cf. "Roteiro," p. 39), whilst, probably, the Portuguese Empire could never have been established but for the terror which he inspired by the signal vengeance which he took upon Calicut for the treachery of its king towards the expedition of Pedr' Alvarez Cabral.²⁹ "Fear and Dread," in other words, "The Power of the Sword," is, indeed, the real foundation of European rule over Asiatic and African races, and Vasco da Gama may, like Mr. Cecil Rhodes in Matabililand, have done a kindness by drowning rebellion in blood.

As Viceroy of India, Da Gama's policy reminds me much of that followed 250 years afterwards by Lord Clive.³⁰ Like Clive, Da Gama was, as Correa (cf. p. 390) points out, "very zealous for the king's revenue, and used to say that men came to India very poor and enriched themselves, and that he, if he could, would make the king rich, as the greatest benefit the people could obtain was to have the king well supplied." "He inspired everybody" (cf. p. 406, Correa)

"with great fear, especially the captains of the forts: for if he found them in fault he would chastise and execute them, and if they remained alive he would send them to the king with the charges against them; because if they were bad, so also would be the officers of their fortress, and the officers of justice and the revenue, and these all together destroyed the people; because the injuries committed by the Moors sprang from the robberies which the captains committed upon them, and therefore no one should go to Portugal to escape from the evil which he had done in India during his time, because as he would chastise the great the small men would be afraid. Therefore, whenever he found a man aggrieved or injured by the great, or by sentences wrongly given, he, would redress it all and

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²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pedro_%C3%81lvares_Cabral

³⁰ Lord Clive, who was well acquainted with the Portuguese language, may have had some knowledge of Da Gama's history from Da Barros, Castanheda, etc.

chastise with strict justice; and he had no need of the gentlemen for fighting, but only for props, to set up one when another was rotten.” Does not this remind us of Lord Clive’s attitude to Johnstone, to the private traders, and to the English officers who resigned their commissions in the mutiny at Fort William of 1765? (Of. Macaulay’s Essays, “Lord Clive,” pp. 535-537, ed. 1869.) Da Gama well proved his sincerity by his conduct to the murderer Fernan Gomes de Lemos, Captain of Ceylon (Correa, pp. 424-5), and to the swindling Governor of Ormuz, D. Duarte de Menezes (p. 408 et seq.).

As a diplomat Vasco da Gama was, perhaps, even more fortunate, for by his alliances with the kings of Cananor and Cochin he was, as I have already pointed out, the first to introduce that system of governing India through her own native princes as feudatories of the imperial power, which we see at work in our own day both in the Dutch East Indies and in the 308 principalities whose rulers, as they have but lately once more shown, are such true and faithful vassals of Victoria Queen-Empress of India. May I end by pointing out that, to his honour be it said, Vasco da Gama never appears to have been guilty of the wanton destruction of a Hindoo temple or of a Mahometan mosque, nor, in that age of intolerance, does

he ever seem to have done any man a wrong merely on account of his religion. He had his reward, for he found faithful friends and loving servants alike amongst Moors, Jews, and even amongst those Nestorian Christians who, in orthodox eyes, were far worse heretics than either.

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Such was the man whom we are met together here this day to honour, three hundred and seventy-four years after he was laid to his rest in the Monastery of St. Antony at Cochin.

Like David from amongst the sheepfolds, like Cecil Rhodes from the coffee-groves of Natal, Vasco da Gama was suddenly and unexpectedly called from the anteroom of a Lisbon palace to take the command of that great undertaking which, in the course of Divine Providence, was not only destined to bind together the Eastern and the Western worlds, but also to give Europe the means of saving her civilization, and that of the empires which she carried in her bosom, from the inrushing flood of barbarism which threatened to overwhelm it in the germ. This undertaking Vasco do Gama faithfully carried out, and to this day we enjoy the fruits of his labours. Are not these sufficient reasons to justify your Council in proposing the resolution which I have been asked to support, and which I trust you will pass with acclamation?

NOTE I. "Lusiad," Canto VII, 3.

Ye Portuguese, as few us ye are brave,
Who never pause your feeble strength to tell;
Ye, who your varied tolls to Death have paid,
To spread abroad the Law of Life eterne;
This is your lot, so Heaven itself decrees,
That ye, poor little flocklet though ye be,
Should do the more in Holy Christentie,
For thus dost Thou, O Christ, exalt humility.

'T is mid these threatening dangers ever nigh,
Amid these days of toil and constant fears,
That they who 're born to be of Fame the friends
Gain honours that fade not and seats above;
Not ever leaning on the moss-grown trunks
That bear the names of noble ancestors,
Nor on their gilded couches, 'twixt the sheets
Of finest sable that Muscovia sends:

Not with new cates, which cooks' racked brains
 devise,
Not with soft idle games to kill the hours,
Not with the varied, infinite delights
Which set a woman's heart in brave men's breasts;
Not with those appetites, ne'er overcome,
Which Fortune aye makes seem so loveable;
She ne'er her thrall allows to haste his step
To dare some deed of prowess virtue bids.

But thou must seek her with thine own stout arm,
And honours win to rightly call thine own,
In watchings and thy good steel girding on;
Bearing the tempests and the cruel waves,
Th' Antarctic's bosom's numbing chills o'ercome
In regions where no sheltering haven opes;
The rotting victuals smiling gulp thou down
Seasoned alone with biting suffering.

Force thou thy face, the paler it doth grow,
To seem the franker, merrier, more care-free,
For all the glowing bullets whistling by
To tear away thy comrade's leg or arm;
'T is thus thy breast with honour callous grows,
And turns alike from honours and from gold,
From honours and from gold that chance hath won,
Chance and not virtue's efforts, just and hard.

'T is thus the mind itself from darkness clears,
And from each trial a god-like calm doth draw,
So that it gazes, as from heaven's seats,
On man's poor feeble stumbling steps below.
Such is the man to whom sound sense gives strength,
Sense sound and never by mere passion swayed,
Who 'll rise (as well he should) to high command
Unsought by him and much against his will.